

DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF A SECURE SMALL MANAGEABLE
ENTERPRISE VLAN, A CASE STUDY FOR I CAN SOUTH SUDAN

BY

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REG: 22/BCN/BU/R/1001

A PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED TO DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTING &
INFORMATICS OF BUGEMA UNIVESITY IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF A
DEGREE IN COMPUTER NETWORKS AND SYSTEMS ADMINISTRATION

SUPERVISOR

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AUGUST, 2024

DECLARATION

I **Betres Wazifu Philip Siligi**, hereby solemnly declare that this is an original project report written by me and that it has never been submitted to any institution of learning for any award. I take the responsibility all the legal and ethical requirements regarding this report.

Signature:

Date.....

/...../.....

APPROVAL

This project report has been submitted for examination with the approval of the following supervisor.

Signed Date

Madam Nantege Hellen, a secure small manageable enterprise VLAN – Supervisor.

Signed Date

Francis Department of Computing and Technology, School of Business, Bugema University.

DEDICATION

This project report is dedicated to God almighty and also to my parents, MR. Sakondo Angelo and, my beloved mother yodita yepeta for their love and support towards the accomplishment of this goal.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, I give glory and thanks to the Almighty God for the gift of life he has granted me throughout the entire period of our research method paper.

Secondly, I wish to extend my sincere gratitude to my Supervisor Madam Nantege Hellen for her endless support and guidance throughout the period I was conducting the research. It has been a great exercise that has made me learn a lot in regards to aspects of network that has shaped me academically.

Lastly, I wish to pass appreciation to my classmates of System project at Bugema University Kampala Campus that supported me in and out of class during this period. Also, I wish to thank Management of I CAN SOUTH SUDAN-Uganda that granted me an opportunity to the system case study with them that has been a great learning experience. May God bless them abundantly.

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Table 1: SHOWS BUDGET FOR THE PROPOSED SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT . 50

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

VLAN: Virtual Local Area Network

LAN: Local Area Network

IP: Internet Protocol

VPNs: virtual Private Networks

VLAN - Virtual Local Area Network

DMZ - Demilitarized Zone

LAN - Local Area Network

IP - Internet Protocol

VPN - Virtual Private Network

IDPS - Intrusion Detection and Prevention System

VLAN - Virtual Local Area Network

VoIP - Voice over Internet Protocol

EIGRP - Enhanced Interior Gateway Routing Protocol

VLSM - Variable Length Subnet Mask

DHCP - Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol

DNS - Domain Name System

iSCSI - Internet Small Computer Systems Interface

ASA - Adaptive Security Appliance

ICS - Industrial Control Systems

IoT - Internet of Things

MLS - Multi-Layer Switching

ON/OFF Model - ON/OFF Model (commonly used in traffic modeling for data networks)

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

SSL - Secure Socket Layer

ftp - File Transfer Protocol

ABSTRACT

This project aimed at implementing Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) to break up broadcast domains into segments, so as to improve network performance and security. A design analysis is carried out to prove that VLAN switch techniques improve the throughput of a network as the graphical results using different network metrics backs this statement. The design and analysis is done on Packet Tracer software which has been proven to be very efficient real time network simulator software by other researchers. The results obtained from the simulations and testing of the security lock was successful, the connectivity of all devices was guaranteed, the network could double or triple without major design changes i.e. it can be flexible at any time

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background of the study

In an era where computer networks are the backbone of modern communication and resource-sharing, understanding their intricacies and ensuring their security is paramount. This proposal aims to address the critical role of computer networks in facilitating communication, data sharing, and resource accessibility. Furthermore, it highlights the significance of robust network design, security measures, and evolving technologies in supporting organizational operations and community development efforts.

The landscape of computer networks encompasses various architectures and topologies, each serving distinct purposes and functions. Dominant models such as client/server and peer-to-peer architectures offer diverse approaches to data distribution and resource allocation. Meanwhile, network topologies like bus, star, mesh, and ring configurations dictate the flow of data within a network structure.

The exponential growth of networks coincided with the emergence of the World Wide Web, revolutionizing communication and enabling services such as websites and peer-to-peer file sharing. While client-server networks dominate the corporate sphere, peer-to-peer networks are prevalent in residential settings.

Security stands as a critical concern in network design, with measures such as firewalls, VPNs, and layer-specific security protocols essential for safeguarding against vulnerabilities. Despite proactive efforts, network administrators face persistent challenges, necessitating continuous adaptation and implementation of robust security measures.

Organizational networks serve as channels for transmitting various data forms, including voice, video, and data. Technological advancements, as emphasized by scholars like Tamirat (2018), Mu'azu and Yahya (2019), and Seifedine and Wassim (2018), advocate for the deployment of technologies such as IP addressing, access control lists, and wireless routing to enhance network efficiency and security.

Moreover, local area networks (LANs) have evolved into strategic assets, supporting critical business operations and facilitating anytime, anywhere access to fast, secure, and reliable services. Simulation software has emerged as a valuable tool for LAN design and maintenance, enabling predictive analysis of network impacts resulting from changes in topology or traffic load.

Amidst this technological landscape, organizations like I CAN South Sudan Uganda have emerged, dedicated to improving the well-being of displaced persons, particularly vulnerable children and women. Founded in 2017 by refugee youth in Bidibidi Refugee Settlement, Yumbe District, Uganda, the organization expanded its services to South Sudan in 2019 and registered in Europe (Norway) in 2023 to enhance donor coordination and resource mobilization.

I CAN South Sudan Uganda envisions a better everyday life for displaced children and is committed to advancing their well-being, protection, survival, and development. Through a holistic approach, the organization aims to instill a sense of meaning, purpose, and hope in the lives of vulnerable children, with the ultimate goal of improving living conditions and fostering opportunities for their return and restart in South Sudan.

The organization operates across thematic areas such as child protection, education, peace-building, livelihood, and environment, guided by values of excellence in performance, partnership, teamwork, integrity, open communications, fear of God, and diversity.

Operating in regions with unstable security situations exposes our organization to constant threats. Without a secure VLAN, sensitive data and resources are vulnerable to cyberattacks and unauthorized access, compromising the safety of our beneficiaries and the integrity of our operations. Limited infrastructure and unreliable connectivity further hinder our ability to effectively manage and monitor our network. However, a secure VLAN would provide a centralized and easily manageable network architecture, overcoming logistical challenges and ensuring seamless communication and resource accessibility across remote locations. Additionally, with limited resources, allocating funds for comprehensive network security measures becomes a challenge. Implementing a secure VLAN offers a cost-effective solution, allowing us to prioritize security without draining

our already limited resources, safeguarding our operations and ensuring continuity of our programs. Furthermore, serving diverse communities with varying cultural backgrounds and languages requires tailored communication strategies. A secure VLAN facilitates effective communication by providing multilingual support and culturally sensitive approaches, ensuring that our messages resonate with all beneficiaries, fostering inclusivity, and trust. Despite these challenges, collaborating with stakeholders across different regions is essential but hindered by bureaucratic processes and communication barriers. By implementing a secure VLAN, we can streamline communication channels, securely share data, and facilitate remote access, improving collaboration and strengthening partnerships for more impactful initiatives.

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1.1 Problem Statement

I CAN South Sudan's current network is affected by operational inefficiencies and security flaws, such as unstable internet connectivity, unprotected entry, and data integrity issues. There was an immediate need for a new VLAN solution to address these problems. With the help of this solution, the company will be able to guarantee data security and network integrity by creating an isolated network environment with improved security measures, effective administration, and best traffic management.

1.2 Aims of the study

This project aims to design and simulate a secure virtual local area network for I CAN South Sudan using Packet Tracer.

1.2.1 Specific Objectives

1. To assess the requirements of the network
2. To design the proposed network
3. To simulate the network design
4. To test and validate

1.3 Scope of the Project

1.3.1 Geographical Scope:

The project will focus on the network infrastructure of I CAN South Sudan's premises, including all physical locations and offices within the organization.

1.3.2 Time Scope:

The project will approximately take 4 months.

1.3.3 Functional scope

The proposed system will offer the organization enhanced network security through methodically configured firewalls. By implementing tough security policies, unauthorized access will be prevented, and sensitive data will be safeguarded from potential breaches. This heightened level of security will provide peace of mind to the organization, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of data transmission within the network. Additionally, the continuous monitoring and adjustment of firewall configurations will enable the

organization to adapt to evolving security threats, maintaining a robust security posture over time. Overall, the system's implementation will strengthen the organization's operational resilience and protect its critical assets from cyber threats, aligning with its commitment to safeguarding sensitive information and ensuring uninterrupted service delivery.

1.4 Significance

1. **Enhanced Network Security:** The project reinforces network security, safeguarding sensitive data and ensuring uninterrupted service delivery to vulnerable populations.
2. **Stability and Flexibility:** By implementing a secure VLAN solution, the project enhances network stability and flexibility, enabling better adaptation to evolving operational needs.
3. **Advancement of Societal Goals:** The initiative drives progress in network infrastructure and cyber-security, facilitating access to essential services and opportunities for marginalized communities.
4. **Academic Contribution:** The project provides valuable insights for academia, serving as a model for studying network security and management practices.
5. **Organizational Excellence:** Demonstrating commitment to excellence, I CAN South Sudan pioneers advanced technologies to fulfill its humanitarian mandate effectively.
6. **Enhanced Collaborations:** Through the secure VLAN implementation, the project fosters partnerships and knowledge exchange within and beyond the organization.
7. **Diverse Impact:** By addressing security and humanitarian needs simultaneously, the project creates a transformative impact on the organization, beneficiaries, and wider society.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This section provides an overview of the existing network system, highlighting its current state. It includes an assessment of strengths and weaknesses based on a review of the current infrastructure, performance, and security measures. Understanding these aspects is crucial for identifying areas of improvement and justifying the need for a secure, manageable enterprise VLAN.

2.1 Current State of the Existing Network System

The current network system provides a foundation for organizational operations, but it has several characteristics that impact its effectiveness.

2.1.1 Positive effects of implementing a secure small manageable enterprise VLAN are numerous.

First of all, it improves security by putting in place strong safeguards that drastically lower the possibility of online dangers like malware, phishing scams, and data breaches. Sensitive information and resources are better safeguarded by separating network traffic and following access control regulations. Second, it results in better performance since faster data transfer and lower latency are caused by effective protocols and optimized network configurations. By guaranteeing rapid access to resources and programs, this boosts productivity for users. Scalability is still another benefit since a well-thought-out VLAN can readily handle the expansion and growth of the company. The network can easily adjust to rising bandwidth and service demands thanks to its scalable infrastructure and adaptable configurations. Finally, streamlined setups and consolidated tools provide simplified management, which makes it simpler for VLAN maintenance and monitoring by IT administrators. Network administration is made possible by the reduction of administrative overhead caused by automated provisioning and troubleshooting processes.

2.1.2 Negative effects associated with implementing a secure small manageable enterprise VLAN.

First, there is a one-time cost that includes staff training, software, and hardware. The budget and resources of the company may be strained by this one-time expense. Second,

complexity develops because maintaining a secure VLAN necessitates establishing network protocols, access control policies, and several security tiers. These systems are more difficult to maintain, which raises the risk of configuration errors that could result in security flaws or network outages. Thirdly, in order to guarantee adherence to and comprehension of updated security procedures and access control mechanisms, user training can be required. Users may unintentionally get around security measures or find it difficult to access resources if they are not properly trained. Finally, there may be incompatibilities between new security protocols and upgraded network infrastructure if they affect hardware and software that is already in use. Ensuring compatibility and easy interaction between it can be difficult and time-consuming to integrate historical and new systems. All things considered, while a secure small controllable company VLAN has many advantages, companies also need to be aware of and take steps to minimize its possible disadvantages, which include compatibility problems, initial cost, complexity, and user training.

2.2 Other Network Systems

Enterprise Network Systems

Comprehensive infrastructures within organizations designed for internal communication, data sharing, and resource management. They include interconnected servers, routers, switches, and security devices to support business operations.

Data Center Networks

High-performance networks supporting large-scale data storage, processing, and distribution. They consist of advanced computing equipment, storage arrays, and networking devices configured for high availability and reliability.

Cloud Computing Networks

On-demand networks providing access to computing resources and services via the internet. They utilize virtualization and distributed computing to offer scalable, flexible, and cost-effective solutions.

Wireless Networks

Networks using radio waves to connect devices without physical cables. Examples include Wi-Fi, cellular networks (3G, 4G, 5G), and satellite networks, providing mobility and remote connectivity.

Industrial Control Systems (ICS)

Networks used in manufacturing, energy, and transportation sectors to monitor and control physical processes and machinery. They consist of sensors, actuators, controllers, and specialized communication protocols.

Internet of Things (IoT) Networks

Networks connecting smart devices and sensors to the internet, enabling data collection, analysis, and automation across various applications. They use wireless communication protocols like Bluetooth and Zigbee for connectivity.

2.2.1 Strengths

Many domains' network systems have a few commonalities, such as scalability and adaptability. Whether they are business, data center, cloud, or Internet of Things networks, most are built to support increasing amounts of data, users, and devices in order to meet rising needs. They provide resource deployment and allocation flexibility, allowing for adaptability to shifting business requirements and advances in technology. Data center and cloud networks are known for their high-performance features, which offer quick data processing and minimal latency. Furthermore, wireless networks and the cloud improve accessibility by enabling remote connections, which fosters productivity and teamwork. Another important asset is reliability, which is particularly useful in business and data center networks since they frequently have fault-tolerant designs and redundant components to reduce downtime. Many networks use advanced security features like access limits and encryption to guard against cyber-attacks and guarantee the accuracy of the data.

2.2.1 Weaknesses

These network systems do, however, have several significant flaws. Complexity is a common difficulty since these systems can be complex to develop, build, and manage,

requiring specialized knowledge and resources. Cost is yet another important factor, especially when it comes to cloud and data center networks, which have high operating, maintenance, and infrastructure costs. Strong security measures don't completely eliminate security flaws, which makes networks vulnerable to data leaks and cyberattacks. Congestion and latency are examples of performance bottlenecks that can impair network performance and user experience. Particularly, data centers use a lot of energy, which raises operational expenses and raises environmental issues. Finally, integration and compatibility might be difficult due to interoperability and compatibility problems, which are particularly common in networks with a variety of technologies and protocols, such as the Internet of Things and industrial control systems.

2.3 Related literature

Several studies have been carried out on Enterprise Network. A study carried out by (Enoch, J. D., Orike, S., & Ahiakwo, C. O., 2019), concentrated on the Enterprise Network Design and Implementation for Airports. In their study they looked at three major areas: quality, safety, and security. Utilities for good network security was presented in their research. The utilities configured to enhance security for the entire network were: proxy server, domain server, hardware firewalls, Mac address port security, and IP access control list. This was to prevent internal and external attacks from gaining access to sensitive departments like the service providers and flight management departments. Cabling system, failover firewalls utility Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol, Pre-boot

Execution Environment, and Domain Name System servers were the technological services used in the air port's network. The performance of the network was improved with these technical tools. Two different internet service vendors' services was deployed for the Air Traffic Control System. The role of the internet service providers was to enable the confirmation of the Air Traffic Control Complex backup operation outside the local network. The "iSCSI initiators" and "iSCSI target" of Windows server backup was used to accomplish this task.

In addition, the web server was hosted on the local network to offer high level security.

According to (Crichigno, J., Bou-Harb, E., & Ghani, N., 2018), A research carried on A comprehensive tutorial on science DMZ, In the research they put together the various services that comprise the enterprise network as a unit, and have structured out security policies such as host web authentication and port security, port security in this context working at a more advanced level. The research work was carried out on Covenant University infrastructure (Senate Building) and the results showed that any Clients who tried to connect to the network and initiated http traffic were redirected to the authentication server for verification of credentials, before being allowed on the network and an email alert was also forwarded to the network administrator. The security services did not impede on network performance with the implementation of Multi-Layer Switching (MLS).

According to (Salihu, 2011), focused on the design of an enterprise network by effectively deploying technologies and protocols as Voice over IP, Access Control Lists, EIGRP routing, Fiber Optics, VLSM for addressing, Inter VLAN routing, Network Address Translation, use of DHCP and wireless routing. This research also investigated the major requirement that necessitates an enterprise network for the benefit of Network Communication Engineers.

According to (Nikoi, S. N., Adu-Boahene, C., & Nsiah-Konandu, A., 2022), enhancing the Design of a Secured Campus Network using Demilitarized Zone and Honey-pot at Uew-kumasi Campus.

According to (Kule, T., & Bakwanamaha, A., 2016), Design of effectively efficient techniques for circumvent wireless network security threats and attacks. The LAN was able to provide internet services and network resources to employees of the firm and restricted access was granted to public users. The study also investigated the vulnerability of the small scale business network. To achieve this goals, the designed network was simulated at the laboratory and the following configurations were made: Virtual Private Network remote client access, wireless connections, firewalls that filters outgoing and incoming IP traffic and the layer 3 and 2 security features. The result of the simulation showed that the network was well secured. It worked for both Internal and remote users' connections through wireless or Internet connection.

According to (Marrocco, 2018), Researched on the development of virtual local area network (VLAN) with a network simulator called Cisco Packet Tracer. In this case study they implementing the method of LAN Switching using VLAN to break up broadcast domains into segments, so as to improve network performance.

According to (Valcourt, S. A., 2017), the Identification of Major Factors in the Deployment of a Science DMZ at Small Institutions. They created a converged network that was geared towards meeting the technical aspect of a business requirement using the top down network design approach. The process was accomplished by carrying out design requirement analysis, logical and physical design, and finally, testing the network. In converged network voice and data traffic perform very well. To accommodate numerous type of traffic, the quality of service was also considered to optimize the network design. The result of the experiment and simulation confirmed that the proposed design met the requirement of quality of service for a converged network, it also showed that it performed better than the existing network design.

According to (Islam, 2022), Designed an Enterprise Network Infrastructure of a City. In the study Cisco packet tracer was used for the design and simulation of a city enterprise network by considering enterprise edge network. The network was design to include three areas in Dhaka, Banani Branch, Motijheel Branch, and Bangladesh: Data center.

According to (Huang, D., Chowdhary, A., & Pisharody, S., 2018), focus on mesh, star, and bus topologies to study various behaviors of the topologies design, and configuration of IP address on network devices and how packets are sent and received in a single network using Cisco packet tracer network simulator.

According to (Tarkaa, N. S., Iannah, P. I., & Iber, I. T., 2017), Designed and Simulated a Local Area Network Using Cisco Packet tracer. The research work described how Cisco Packet tracer was used to simulate the LAN model for the College of Engineering in the University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Nigeria. The study offered detailed explanation on the use of Virtual Local Area Networks to segment the network for each departments in the college of engineering. It also analyze the transfer of packets on a network.

According to (Ince, N., & Topuz, E. (Eds.), 2020), explore genetic algorithm in other to use it for network topology design from hierarchical network model. It was made up of lower physical topology and upper logical topology. The self- similar traffic was modeled using the ON/OFF model and the self-similar traffic information on the network was described by the logical topology. The network connection of devices and links were represented in the lower physical topology. This study proposed a genetic algorithm technique for developing a novel network topology design in order to obtain a network with minimum cost and delay under certain reliability. In conclusion a practical test was carried out to verify the accuracy and the effectiveness of the network topology design. The result of the test showed that the techniques was better than the referenced methods.

According to (al., 2020) The importance of secure networks will continue to be of very importance to anyone designing, implementing or managing a network infrastructure. Securing of the network includes security of data and information and also security of the infrastructure on which there can be theft, tampering of devices hence the disruption of information and services is kept to the minimum, a secure local area network is one that has acceptable integrity, confidentiality and is available to the intended users.

In case a hacker wants log into a system or network as sometimes the case is, sometimes there is nothing one¹⁴ can do to stop it since they have advanced tools in their hands but what can be done is to reduce all areas by making it harder for the intruder to breach the system's security.

According to (al. A. e., 2014) Designed and Simulated a Secure and Scalable LAN. In the research they put together the various services that comprise the enterprise network as a unit, and have structured out security policies such as host web authentication and port security, port security in this context working at a more advanced level. The research work was carried out on Covenant University infrastructure (Senate Building) and the results showed that any Clients who tried to connect to the network and initiated http traffic were redirected to the authentication server for verification of credentials, before being allowed on the network and an email alert was also forwarded to the network administrator. The security services did not impede on network performance with the implementation of Multi-Layer Switching (MLS).

According to Mu'azu and Yahya (2015), focused on the design of a network by effectively deploying technologies and protocols as Voice over IP, Access Control Lists, Fiber Optics, VLSM for addressing, Inter VLAN routing, Network Address Translation, use of DHCP and wireless routing. This research also investigated the major requirement that necessitates an enterprise network for the benefit of Network Communication Engineers. Seifedine and Wassim (2014), proposed a secure design and implementation of a network and system in Windows environment using the latest technology. Reviewed the latest product with an application to an enterprise with worldwide branches are given.

Erik and Tamirat (2013), developed a Local Area Network (LAN) that was secured for a small-scale business. The LAN was able to provide internet services and network resources to employees of the firm and restricted access was granted to public users. The study also investigated the vulnerability of the small-scale business network. To achieve this goal, the designed network was simulated at the laboratory and the following configurations were made: Virtual Private Network remote client access, wireless connections, firewalls that filters outgoing and incoming IP traffic and the layer 3 and 2 security features. The result of the simulation showed that the network was well secured. It worked for both Internal and remote users' connections through wireless or Internet connection.

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ON/OFF model and the self-similar traffic information on the network was described by the logical topology. The network connection of devices and links were represented in the lower physical topology. This study proposed a genetic algorithm technique for developing a novel network topology design in order to obtain a network with minimum cost and delay under certain reliability. In conclusion a practical test was carried out to verify the accuracy and the effectiveness of the network topology design. The result of the test showed that the techniques was better than the referenced methods.

According Kuhn et al., (2005). A secure local area network is one that has acceptable integrity, confidentiality and is available to the intended users. In case a hacker wants log into a system or network as sometimes the case is, sometimes there is nothing one can do to stop it since they have advanced tools in their hands but what can be done is to reduce all areas by making it harder for the intruder to breach the system's security. The importance of secure networks will continue to be of very importance to anyone designing, implementing or managing a network infrastructure. Securing of the network includes security of data and information and also security of the infrastructure on which there can be theft, tampering of devices hence the disruption of information and services is kept to the minimum,

According to Rao and Choudhury (2010), Network can be physical or wireless interconnection of computers and communication devices that allow many users to share data or information or even resources within a defined geographical area, either a building or a group of buildings. In this research the LAN. In terms of security issues, organizations experience threats such crushing of databases due to low security settings, and computers being attacked by viruses and worms (Emanuel and Sife 2008).

According to (Oecd, 2003), organizations have the responsibility to build up a tradition and a norm for confidentiality, data protection and also data/information security. Information/data protection is not just a technical issue; it also involves issues such as training, sensitizing and educating staff and users for privacy, reducing or limiting access to user identifiable information (Fisser, 2001). Computers require up to date antivirus software, most of which are very expensive.

Identified Knowledge Gap

The Several studies carried out on the design and simulation of an Enterprise Network, did not handle the physical and logical design of an enterprise network for the proposed case study but demonstrated the generalized design implementation with a network simulator. None of the researchers included the use of Cisco

Adaptive Security Appliance (ASA) device, which is a dedicated network security hardware that prevents both internal and external attacks on the network. Furthermore, none of the researchers developed a customized encryption and decryption solution to secure the database of the proposed case study. Finally, it was observed that none of the researchers included the bill of engineering measurement and evaluation of the proposed designed case study to enable IT/Network Engineers deploy the proposed design.

2.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the review of existing literature underscores the importance of both leveraging established network design principles and addressing the unique needs of specific organizations like I CAN South Sudan. The strengths of current network systems, such as scalability, high performance, and advanced security measures, demonstrate their critical role in supporting modern enterprises and enhancing operational efficiency. However, the complexities and costs associated with these systems, along with the persistent challenges of security vulnerabilities and interoperability issues, highlight the need for a tailored approach.

The identified knowledge gaps, particularly the lack of specialized solutions and detailed design considerations for unique organizational contexts, emphasize the necessity for a more targeted and customized approach. To optimize network performance, security, and scalability for I CAN South Sudan, it is essential to integrate advanced security technologies, develop bespoke encryption solutions, and perform comprehensive engineering evaluations. Addressing these areas will not only bridge the current gaps but also ensure that the network infrastructure effectively supports the organization's specific needs and future growth. As the network landscape continues to evolve, focusing on these tailored solutions will be crucial in enhancing both the resilience and efficiency of network systems within such specialized environments.

2.5 Proposed System

The proposed secure VLAN for I CAN South Sudan will incorporate advanced firewalls to ensure a robust defense against unauthorized access and potential cyber threats. These firewalls will be configured to monitor and control incoming and outgoing network traffic based on predetermined security rules. While the system will effectively use firewalls to enforce security policies and protect sensitive data, it will not include Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS). The absence of IDPS means that while proactive measures are in place to block unwanted traffic and threats, the system will not have real-time monitoring and automated responses to detect and prevent active attacks. This design focuses on providing strong perimeter defense through firewalls but may need supplementary solutions for comprehensive network security.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGIES

3.0 Introduction

This chapter delineates the methodologies employed to design and implement a secure VLAN for I CAN South Sudan. It outlines the approaches for gathering requirements, utilizing design tools, simulating and implementing the network, and testing and validating the system.

3.1 Gathering Requirements

Approach: The requirements for the secure VLAN at I CAN South Sudan will be gathered through two primary methods: interviews and observations.

3.1.1 Interviews

Key stakeholders will provide information about the project's objectives and technical requirements, with an emphasis on the advantages of data and information security as well as the needs for network deployment. To learn about the demands and problems facing the network, we spoke with ten important stakeholders.

3.1.2 Observation

The current network infrastructure will be analyzed to determine areas that require upgrading and to evaluate current capabilities. WE spent two weeks observing the current network, paying particular attention to performance and infrastructure.

3.2 Design Tools

Packet Tracer software will be utilized. This tool allows for the creation of a logical representation of the network topology, enabling visualization and analysis of the proposed VLAN design. Packet Tracer's simulation capabilities will also aid in assessing network performance and identifying potential issues before implementation.

3.3 Simulation and Implementation

Simulation: Once the VLAN design is conceptualized using Packet Tracer, simulation will be performed to validate its functionality and effectiveness. This phase involves testing various network configurations, protocols, and security measures to ensure they meet the established requirements.

Implementation: Following successful simulation, the implementation of the designed VLAN will commence, utilizing the insights gained from the simulation to guide the deployment process. This phase involves translating the simulated design into actionable steps for deployment.

3.4 Testing and Validation

Testing: After implementation, the VLAN will undergo rigorous testing to verify its performance and security. Testing procedures will include using tools such as ping and traceroute (tracert) to assess network connectivity and responsiveness. Additionally, security measures will be evaluated through penetration testing and vulnerability assessments to identify any weaknesses and ensure robust protection against cyber threats.

Figure 1: Testing Using Ping Command

Validation: Validation of the system will be conducted by troubleshooting any issues encountered during testing and verifying that the VLAN operates according to the established requirements.

Figure 2: Validation

Conclusion

Chapter Three outlines the methodologies employed throughout the design and implementation of the secure VLAN for I CAN South Sudan. By gathering requirements through interviews and observations, utilizing design tools like Packet Tracer, simulating and implementing the network, and testing and validating the system, we ensure the successful deployment of a reliable and secure network infrastructure that meets the organization's needs.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS, ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

4.0 Introduction

This chapter entails the realization of the logically designed network. It shows the technologies used to implement a VLAN network with proper security. The design and implementation in the I CAN SOUTH SUDAN were carried out in order to provide the best approach the new VLAN which is cost effective.

A VLAN security measure was highly emphasized by implementing organization policies that suite the operation of services on the network. The administrator can monitor and prevent unauthorized access into the network by configuring firewall at the network interface. This prevents the host from security threats and provides a secured network of higher transmissions integrity.

4.1 Conceptual frame work

Figure 3: Conceptual frame work

4.2 System study

This involved reviewing the then network to get a better understanding of how the current network function. This was useful because it enabled expose the weaknesses of the current

network which also include the security weakness thus the need of a proposed new network to overcome these weaknesses.

4.2.1 The Existing Network

The existing network of I CAN SOUTH SUDAN faces significant challenges including security vulnerabilities, operational inefficiencies, limited resources, communication barriers, and the need for centralized management. These shortcomings prompted the organization to request a new system to address these issues and support its humanitarian mandate effectively.

4.2.2 Weaknesses of the Existing Network

The current network system has notable weaknesses that could compromise its effectiveness and security. One of the most critical weaknesses is its limited security measures. Without robust security protocols in place, the network is vulnerable to cyber threats such as malware, phishing attacks, and data breaches. Moreover, outdated infrastructure may hinder performance and pose compatibility issues with newer technologies. Additionally, poor scalability could impede the organization's ability to accommodate future growth and expansion. The lack of redundancy and inadequate disaster recovery preparedness further exacerbate the system's vulnerabilities, leaving it susceptible to downtime and data loss in the event of hardware failures or catastrophic events.

4.3. Analysis of the Proposed Network System

This section describes the user and network requirements. The requirements themselves are the descriptions of the network services and constraints that are generated during the requirements engineering process. The user requirements were divided into two categories mainly functional and non-functional requirements.

4.3.1. Functional Requirements

Functional requirements are statements of services the network should provide, how the network should function, run and how the network should behave in particular situations. The requirements made sure:

- The network should be secure. It should protect the data that is transmitted over it, as well as data stored on the devices that connect to it.
- The network should stay up all the time, even in the event of failed links, equipment failure, and overloaded conditions.
- The network should be easy to modify to adapt to network growth and general business changes.
- Troubleshooting the network should be easy. Finding and fixing a problem should not be too time-consuming.

4.3.2. Non-Functional Requirements

These are qualities that add value to the network system. They describe constraints on the services or functions offered by the network system such as timing constraints, constraints on the development process, standards, etc. These include:

- The network is easy to learn and use.
- The external unauthorized users cannot access the private network.
- The network is easy to maintain.
- The network is able to update the administrator in case of malfunctioning.

4.4. Network System Design

This is the process of converting the network specifications into an executable functioning network system. This section describes the design and development process of the Network LAN for I CAN SOUTH SUDAN.

4.5. Fundamental Design Goals

When examined carefully, network requirements translate into four fundamental network design goals:

- Scalability - Scalable network designs are able to grow to include new user groups and remote sites and can support new applications without impacting the level of service delivered to existing users.
- Availability - A network designed for availability is one that delivers consistent, reliable performance, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. Additionally, the failure of a

single link or piece of equipment should not significantly impact network performance.

- Security - Security is a feature that must be designed into the network, not added on after the network is complete. Planning the location of security devices, filters, and firewall features is critical to safeguarding network resources.
- Manageability - No matter how good the initial network design is, the available network staff must be able to manage and support the network. A network that is too complex or difficult to maintain cannot function effectively and efficiently. To meet the four fundamental design goals, a network must be built on an architecture that allows for both flexibility and growth.

4.6. Network System Design

The following is the layout of the new network VLAN for I CAN SOUTH SUDAN. The layout shows how devices and new features were implemented on the new network system. It shows in details how the VLANs and other security measures will work. The layout diagram also shows what network devices will be found in the organization.

Figure 4: Network Design Overview

4.7 Project requirements

The high-level projects requirements are project facilities, software requirements and hardware requirements.

4.7.1 Hardware requirements

The following are the hardware requirements for the proposed VLAN;

Router as for simulation purposes to use the high end, router provided by Cisco packet tracer.

Switch, as for simulation purposes to use the high end.

Cables provided by Cisco packet tracer as per the required type of cable required for each type of connection

4.7.2 Simulation Tool (Cisco Packet Tracer)

Cisco Packet tracer is a network simulation tool provided by CISCO Systems to student and Administrators to experiment. It can be used for simulation purposes, visualization purposes and even collaboration capabilities. It helps to understand any complex network technology concepts.

It can also be used to design and simulate any network by interconnecting various networking equipment and also one can run the various network tests to ensure the connectivity and communication between different networking devices is as per the set requirements.

Various protocols e.g. Telnet, secure socket layer (SSL), ftp e.tc can be used and run on the Cisco packet tracer simulation tool.

4.7.2 Network Topology

The following is the layout of the new VLAN network of the I CAN SOUTH SUDAN. The layout shows how devices and new features were implemented on the new network system. It shows in details how users will be using the network and how each office is going to use that new function. The layout diagram also shows what network devices will be found in the I CAN SOUTH SUDAN organization.

The below is the picture depict the New VLAN

Figure 5: Complete Configured VLAN

CHAPTER FIVE

IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

5.0 Introduction

This chapter describes the implementation of the designed secure VLAN with DMZ for I CAN South Sudan. The implementation covers the deployment of VLANs, firewalls, and DMZ setup, followed by a comprehensive testing strategy to ensure all components work as expected.

5.1 Implementation

The implementation phase involved configuring network devices such as routers, switches, and firewalls, along with software installation and setup. The following were the key steps in the implementation:

VLAN Configuration: VLANs were created for different departments using Cisco switches. Inter-VLAN routing was enabled to allow communication between VLANs as per the access control policies.

DMZ Setup: The DMZ was configured with dedicated servers for public-facing services, such as the company website and mail servers.

Firewall Rules: Firewalls were configured to enforce strict security policies between the internal network and the DMZ.

VPN Deployment: A secure VPN solution was implemented to allow remote workers to securely access the internal network.

Network Monitoring Tools: Network monitoring software was installed to provide real-time insights into network traffic and detect any potential security threats.

5.2 Testing

Testing was conducted at various levels to ensure the network met the design requirements:

5.2.1 Unit Testing

Individual network components such as VLANs, firewalls, and VPN configurations were tested separately to verify that they functioned as expected.

5.2.2 Integration Testing

The integration of all network components, including the VLANs, DMZ, and VPN, was tested to ensure smooth communication between the different network segments.

The Below is the integration test

Figure 6: Integration Testing

5.2.3 System Testing

The entire network system was tested in a simulated environment to verify overall functionality. This included stress testing under different load conditions to ensure the network's performance and reliability.

The picture below depict the system test

Figure 7: System Testing

5.2.4 User Acceptance Testing

User acceptance testing was conducted with the staff of I CAN South Sudan to ensure the system met their requirements. Feedback from users was collected and adjustments were made to enhance usability and performance.

The below picture shows the communication between different department using ping command

Figure 8: User Acceptance Testing

5.2.5 Test Results

The results from the testing phases showed that the network was performing as expected. Screenshots of the test results, including network traffic logs and firewall configuration tests, are documented in this section.

The picture displays the results of the communication between devices on the network

Figure 9: Test Results

CHAPTER SIX

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

In this study, Routers, switches, and the necessary servers were configured and during the realization of this network topology, Packet Tracer software was used. The actual router, switch programming was made of identical devices. VLANs are defined, these VLANs are configured with the necessary equipment.

6.2 Significance

After the implementation and testing of the network; Troubleshooting became easy because there were no complex routing interactions. It was guaranteed that the devices could reach every point of the network, which mean that the connectivity of all devices was guaranteed. The network could double or triple without major design changes i.e. it can be flexible at any time.

6.3 Conclusion

Recent technological advances will require more reliable and practical ways to design networks. The goal of this project, which is to be an enterprise network, is to ensure that no device stays on its own, that connectivity is fast, and that the addition of devices must not hinder packet transmission, added interfaces that are not intended for access must be blocked. It can be concluded that these objectives have been achieved and that the work and troubleshooting standards have been fully met.

6.4 Limitations

When evaluating enterprise network governance solutions, design simulators should consider the following:

- a) Fiber Optic Modules must be created in the 3560 Layer 3 Switch.
- b) Generic routers should have modules that enable telephony service, not just 2811 routers.
- c) Servers should have interfaces that allow VoIP configuration.

d) Access points should have the Command Line Interface (CLI).

6.5 Recommendations for Future Work

a) Additional Access Control Lists (ACLs) must be implemented throughout the network to provide robust end-to-end security.

b) IPv6 addressing can be implemented to overcome restrictions on the number of hosts that can be used due to the available address space.

c) Additional configuration can be implemented on the network to enable video conferencing in addition to the currently available VoIP features.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: INTERVIEW GUIDE

TOPIC: A SECURE SMALL MANAGEABLE ENTERPRISE VLAN FOR I CAN SOUTH SUDAN

Dear Sir/ Madam,

I am Students of Bugema University pursuing a Bachelor's of science in Computer network and system administration, and diploma in Information Technology conducting a study to gather requirements and analyze them to obtain the requirement specifications for development of a secure small manageable enterprise VLAN using DMZ for I CAN SOUTH SUDAN. The study is purely for academic purposes and the information given will be treated with utmost confidentiality. I therefore, humbly request you to spare some time and answer the following questions.

SECTION A: BIO-DATA

Tick or write answers in full where applicable.

1. Gender

a) Male b) Female

2. Marital status:

a) Single b) Married

3. Age bracket (years)

a) 18-20 b) 21-30 c) 31-40 d) 41- above

4. Level of education attained

- a) Primary b) secondary c) Tertiary d) University

SECTION.B TECHNICIANS'

System Reliability: How reliable is the VLAN system?

- Excellent
 Good
 Average
 Poor

Technical Challenges: Any hurdles faced during VLAN and DMZ setup?

- Yes
 No

Security and Performance Tools: What tools are used for ensuring VLAN security and performance?

- Monitoring Software
 Firewall
 Antivirus
 Other

(Specify).....

Technical Suggestions: Any suggestions for technical improvements in the VLAN setup?

- Yes
 No

SECTION C USER

User Experience: How's your experience accessing resources within the VLAN system?

Excellent

Good

Average

Poor

Guidance on Security: Did you receive sufficient guidance on securely using the VLAN and DMZ?

Yes

No

Impact on Collaboration: How has the VLAN system impacted collaboration and communication?

Positive Impact

Neutral

Negative Impact

Feature Requests: Any user-friendly features you'd like to see in the VLAN system?

Yes

No

Thank you for the co-operation

APPENDICES 2: TIME SCHEDULED

Table 1: TIME SCHEDULED

# Activity	Start	Ends	Duration
1 Proposal writing	11-Feb-24	10-Mar-24	28
2 User system requirements	13-Mar-24	22-Mar-24	9
3 system design	23-Mar-24	14-Apr-24	22
4 Implementation	15-Apr-24	4-May-24	19
5 Testing	5-May-24	10-May-24	5
6 Report writing	11-May-24	18-May-24	7
7 Supervision	19-May-24	22-May-24	3
8 System presentation	23-May-24	24-May-24	1

APPENDICES 3: GANTT CHART

Table 2: SHOWS BUDGET FOR THE PROPOSED SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

S/No	Item	Cost UGX
1	Transport	100,000
2	Hardware	80,000
3	Software	50,000
4	Typing and Printing	200,000
5	Airtime	20,000
6	Lunch	120,000
	Total	570,000 UGX